

CREDIT RISK MANAGEMENT AND DEPOSIT MONEY BANK'S PERFORMANCE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study examines Credit Risk Management and Deposit money Bank's Performance in Nigeria. This paper set out to investigate the impact of credit risk management on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria using the Correlation and the panel Least Square regression techniques. Data for the study were sourced from the CBN Statistical Bulletin for the period 2006 to 2018. Our findings demonstrate succinctly that the selected credit risk management indicators under study significantly impact on the performance of deposit money banks measured as return on equity, return on assets, respectively. However, the findings suggest that ROA is a better measure of performance than ROE. And in conclusion, Banks should not always be in a rush in approving loans for prospective borrowers but should first determine the credit worthiness of the customer so as to aid quick pay back of the loan. This will not only reduce the massive loan losses often witnessed by them, it will also reduce their huge provision for loss loans and thereby improve their performance over time.

Keywords: Panel Least Square, Credit Risk and Performance.

Introduction

Bank failures in Nigeria and other emerging economies have been attributed to improper lending practices, lack of experience, organizational and informational systems to adequately assess credit risk in the falling economy (Gil-Diaz, 1994, Ahmad & Ariff, 2007; Kolapo, Ayeni & Oke, 2012). There is sufficient empirical evidence that poor performance is manifest in banks as indicted by low bank performance indicators including: high levels of credit risk, poor quality loans, limited and or inadequate capitalization, operational inefficiencies, higher incidences of non-performing loans, higher levels of liquidity risk, and so on. Although these are mentioned as constraints affecting banks' performance, they are based on a few studies and non-elaborate methods to generate sufficient and valid conclusions. This study therefore becomes an extension of the few studies undertaken with a view to generating more and further information based on empirical evidence on deposit money banks. The purpose of this paper therefore, is to ascertain whether there is any significant relationship between credit risk management and the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

The excruciating effect of the global economic meltdown of 2007 – 2008 has called for the urgent need to institute improved sartorial informs and policies geared towards insulating financial systems from external and

internal shocks. Nigeria, through the central bank responded in this direction by reinforcing the existing Deposit Insurance Scheme (DIS) and putting in place, support programs for banks that made provisions for liquidity, government guarantees of all deposits, interbank lending and the recapitalization of ailing banks through the Asset management Corporation of Nigeria (AMCON). DIS, also referred to as deposit guarantee system (Alyeksyeyev & Mazur, 2018) is a mutual insurance system funded by insured banks and administered either through privately held agencies or through government-controlled agencies that guarantees depositors funds that are held in the insured financial institutions/banks (Ume, Oleka & Obasikene, 2017; Ani & Ogar, 2018). In addition to causing individual banks to fail, bank runs can have a ripple effect and trigger full-blown contagion. Banks are connected through interbank lending and other risk-sharing arrangements. Fears about the insolvency of one bank can spread into a generalized contagion causing multiple banks to fail.

Usually, in the event of total collapse or failure on the part of any insured bank, depositors are promptly reimbursed where the DIS in place is effective and efficient. The DIS has evolved as a result of the need to offer some form of protection to depositors who stood the risk of losing their hard-earned money in the event of bank failures. Alford (2010, 2012); asserts that a well-designed DIS should possess proper mechanisms to ensure the availability of sufficient funds to promptly reimburse depositors in the event of failure and equally defray operating expenses of the system as evidenced by the experiences of other countries. Where the existing DIS is not sufficiently funded, there might be problems relating to delays in reimbursing depositors and/or resolving the aftermaths of bank failures which certainly has grave consequences on the confidence and credibility of the system (Demirguc-Kunt & Kane, 2002; Nijskens & Wagner, 2011).

Deposit insurance is widely adopted across the globe and constitutes an integral part of the financial safety net provided to the banking system. During the global financial crisis, a number of countries introduced new deposit insurance schemes or extended the scope and coverage of existing schemes to restore confidence and to avert potential contagious runs on their banking sectors. These interventions rekindled the debate on the impact of deposit insurance on financial stability and the moral hazard costs associated with government intervention. One of its economic benefits is to reduce the contagion run on the banking system. Nigeria held an explicit DIS in 1998, and was administered by the NDIC as a financial safety-net set up to mitigate systemic crisis. From the onset, Nigeria, through the NDIC adopted an ex-ante funding arrangement for the scheme. Available statistics from the records of NDIC indicates that the accumulated Deposit Insurance Fund (herein after - DIF) under the scheme (DIS) exhibits an increasing growth trend over the years but arguably, this growth may not have significantly staunched the tide of distress and failures in the Nigerian banking industry. For instance, the country witnessed a number of bank failures between 1994 and 2006 (in what is now referred to as the pre consolidation banking crises). A total of 49 banks failed with the highest occurring in the year 1998 which witnessed a total of 26 bank failures. According to NDIC (2006), evidence from the 2004 on-site audit revealed that the aggregate volume of assets in the balance sheets of failed banks amounted to ₦165.90 billion, whereas the balance for liabilities stood at ₦198.01 billion. The higher balance for total liabilities as compared to total assets is indicative of imminent insolvency (World Bank, 2016; Mbarek & Hmaied, 2011; Chu, 2011), thereby raising stern concerns on the safety of depositors' funds.

It is important to note that the effectiveness of deposit insurance relies crucially on the assumption that the insurance is viewed to be credible by depositors. If depositors believe that there is even a small possibility that the insurer will run out of funds, then it becomes rational for the investors to be the first in line to withdraw

their deposits. All insurance schemes are under-funded in the sense that they do not hold funds to fully cover all potential losses. But, there is typically an expectation that the state would provide a full backstop should such a need arise during a crisis. However, this requires the state to have the political will and more importantly, the economic resources to intervene to fund depositor losses.

In countries with large banking sectors and deteriorating public finances, intervention is not always a viable option owing to underfunding challenges. In some cases, if bank runs are a result of liquidity shortages as opposed to solvency problems, it is only natural to ask whether a similar function can be performed by a central bank working as a lender of last resort. In most countries central banks are allowed to provide temporary liquidity to the banking sector to relieve short-term frictions that might result in a bank run (Diamond & Dybvig, 1983).

Prior to the implementation of state sponsored deposit insurance, clearing houses in the early nineteenth century played a similar role in the United States. The goal of the clearing houses was to ensure the continuous flow of transactions in the banking system during times of distress. The earliest state sponsored insurance schemes date back to 1829 when the state of New York created a safety fund for banks operating in New York. The safety fund was meant to insure bank notes and major bank liabilities, but failed to provide protection during the panic of 1837. Over the years from 1831 to 1859, Vermont, Michigan, Indiana and Ohio also set up insurance schemes with mixed results. From 1908 to 1917 eight more states passed deposit guarantee legislation. All eight guarantee funds failed during the 1920s starting with Washington's fund in 1921. Of the eight, all but the Texas guarantee fund let depositors with uninsured losses (Calomiris, 1989). The Great Depression resulted in the failure of thousands of banks which led to the establishment of the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation (FDIC) in 1933.

Currently, over 107 countries have some form of explicit deposit insurance, up from 93 in 2013; according to the Bank Regulation and Supervision Survey (BRSS) conducted by the World Bank. Some of the recent changes have been implemented in the aftermath of the global financial crisis. During the crisis, several countries including Australia and Singapore introduced explicit deposit insurance schemes for the first time. Other countries, like the United States and Spain, substantially increased the coverage limit, while others like Germany and Ireland introduced unlimited coverage in order to restore confidence in the markets. Explicit deposit insurance is widely adopted across the globe and is now a Standard policy of bank regulators and supervisors. The then financial crisis has reinforced the importance of deposit insurance in promoting stability and its role in the overall financial safety and provided to the banking sector. Nigeria, through the NDIC adopted an ex-ante funding arrangement for the scheme. Available statistics from the records of NDIC indicates that the accumulated Deposit Insurance Fund (herein after - DIF) under the scheme (DIS) exhibits an increasing growth trends over the years but arguably, this growth may not have significantly staunched the tide of distress and failures in the Nigerian banking industry. For instance, the country witnessed a number of bank failures between 1994 and 2006 (in what is now referred to as the pre consolidation banking crises). A total of 49 banks failed with the highest occurring in the year 1998 which witnessed a total of 26 bank failures. According to NDIC (2006), evidence from the 2004 on-site audit revealed that the aggregate volume of assets in the balance sheets of failed banks amounted to N165.90 billion, whereas, the balance for liabilities stood at N198.01 billion. The increase in liabilities over total asset indicated an imminent failure in the banks (World Bank, 2016; Mbarek & Hmaied, 2011; Chu, 2011), thereby creating panic on the safety of depositors' funds. More so, there

seem to be moral hazard costs associated with government intervention through the deposit insurance fund to bail out failed banks and prevent contagion run on banks and prevent contagion run on banks, to ensure confidence in the system.

The existence of deposit insurance guarantees that depositors will get their money back should their bank fail. This assurance brings confidence to the market, but at the same time distorts incentives of both bank managers and depositors, resulting in the well-known economic problem of moral hazard. The incentive distortions are two-fold. First, deposit insurance gives insured banks incentives to take on riskier investments, since economic profits from higher risk-taking are privately captured by the bank but losses are socialized through the deposit insurance fund. Second, since depositors are protected when a bank fails, their incentive to monitor the financial condition of their bank is significantly reduced. It is against this background that this paper studies Banks credit risks Management and Deposit Money Bank's Performance in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

Conceptual/Theoretical Review

Risk to the bank means the perceived uncertainty connected with some event. For example, will the customer renew his or her loan? Will deposit liabilities grow next month? Will the bank's stock price and its earnings increase in the future? Are interest rates going to rise or fall next week and will the bank lose income or value if they do? Bankers may be most interested in achieving high stock values and high profitability, but none can fail to pay attention to the risks they are accepting as well. Bankers are concerned with many types of risks such as credit risk, liquidity risk, market risk, interest rate risk, earnings risk, foreign exchange risk and solvency risk. (Rose, 1999;

Chen, 2012; Kargi, 2011).

A bank exists not only to accept deposits but also to grant credit facilities and therefore is inevitably exposed to credit risk, in other words, the intermediation function of a bank naturally exposes them to credit risk: credit risk is by far the most significant risk faced by banks and the success of their business depends on accurate measurement and efficient management of credit risk more than any other risks (Gieseche, 2024). Chen and Pan (2012) argue that credit risk is the degree of value fluctuations in debt instruments and derivatives due to changes in the underlying credit quality of borrowers and counterparties. Coyle (2000) defines credit risk as losses from the refusal or inability of credit customers to pay what is owed in full and on time. Credit risk is the exposure faced by banks when a borrower (customer) defaults in honouring debt obligations on due date or at maturity. This risk interchangeably called 'counterparty risk' is capable of putting the bank in distress if not adequately managed. The credit risk management implications are measures employed by banks to avoid or minimize the adverse effect of credit risk. A sound credit risk management framework is crucial for banks so as to exchange profitability and guarantee survival.

The main sources of credit risk include, limited institutional capacity, inappropriate credit policies, volatile interest rates, poor management, inappropriate laws, low capital and liquidity levels, direct lending, massive licensing of banks, poor loan underwriting, laxity in credit assessment, poor lending practices, government interference and inadequate supervision by the central bank (Kithinji, 2010). An increase in bank credit risk gradually leads to liquidity and solvency problems. Credit risk may increase if the bank lends to borrowers it does not have adequate knowledge about.

Credit risk management maximizes bank's risk adjusted rate of return by maintaining credit risk exposure within acceptable limits in order to provide framework for understanding the impact of credit risk management on banks' profitability (Kargi, 2011). Demircug-Kunt and Huzinga (1999) opined that credit risk management is in two-fold which includes, the realization that after losses have occurred, the losses become unbearable and the developments in the field of financing commercial paper, securitization and other non-bank competition which push banks to find viable loan borrowers. Lindergren (1987) argued that the key principles in credit risk management process are sequenced as follows: establishment of a clear structure, allocation of responsibility, processes have to be prioritized and disciplined, responsibilities should be clearly communicated and accountability assigned. The implications for communicated and accountability assigned.

Empirical Review

Kargi (2011) evaluated the impact of credit risk on the profitability of Nigerian banks using financial ratios as measures of bank performance and credit risk data were collected from the annual reports and accounts of sampled banks from 2004-2008 and analyzed using descriptive, correlation and regression techniques. The findings revealed that credit risk management has a significant impact on the profitability of Nigerian banks. It concluded that banks' profitability is inversely influenced by the levels of loans and advances, non-performing loans and deposits thereby exposing them to great risk of illiquidity and distress. Epure and Lafuente (2012) examined bank performance in the presence of risk for Costa-Rican banking industry during 1998-2007. The results showed that performance improvements follow regulatory changes and that risk explains differences in banks and non-performing loans negatively affect efficiency and return on assets while the capital adequacy ratio has a positive impact on the next interest margin.

Kithinji (2010) assessed the effect of credit risk management on the profitability of commercial banks in Kenya. Data on the amount of credit, level of non-performing loans and profits were collected for the period 2004 to 2008. The findings revealed that the bulk of the profits of commercial banks are not influenced by the amount of credit and non-performing loans, therefore suggesting that other variables other than credit and non-performing loans impact on profits. Chen and Pan (2012) examined the credit risk efficiency of 34 Taiwanese commercial banks over the period 2005-2008. Their study used financial ratios to assess credit risk and their analysis employed Data Development Analysis (DEA). The credit risk parameters were credit risk technical efficiency (CR-TE), credit risk allocative efficiency (CR-AE), and credit risk cost efficiency (CR-CE). The results indicated that only one bank is efficient in all types of efficiencies over the sample period. Overall, the DEA results show relatively low average efficiency levels in CR-TE, CR-AE and CR-CE in 2008.

Furthermore, Felix and Claudine (2008) investigated the relationship between bank performance and credit risk management focusing on emerging economies. It could be inferred from their findings that return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA) both measuring profitability were inversely related to the ratio of non-performing loans to total loans and advances of financial institutions thereby leading to a decline in profitability.

Ahmed, Takeda and Shawn (1998) in their study found that loan loss provision has a significant positive influence on non-performing loans. For the authors therefore, an increase in loan loss provision indicates an increase in credit risk and deterioration in the quality of loans consequently affecting bank performance adversely.

3. Methodology

The research design adopted in this study is the causal research design, as it is meant to investigate and analyse cause and effect relationship between two or more variables, namely credit risk management and performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Measurement of Variables

Dependent Variable

In this study, performance is the dependent variable represented by return on total assets (ROTA), defined as profit after tax divided by total assets; return on equity (ROE), defined as profit after tax divided by equity. The above performance indicators have been used extensively in previous studies and with satisfactory result (Said & Turin, 2011; Okafor, 2012; Aziz, Ibrahim & Isa 2009; Ogbulu, 2012, Ogbulu & Eze, 2016). Glonti & Vashakmadze, 2018; Alyeksyeyev & Mazur, 2018; Jameaba, 2018) with very few empirical researches on economies in sub-Saharan Africa (Ani & Ogar, 2018; Cheng & Ellyne, 2011; Anyanwu, 1997).

Independent Variables

The independent variable for this study is Credit risk. It is given as the risk of the banks customers’ failure to meet their repayment obligation before the due date after accessing credit from the banks. Credit risk management is a major challenge to deposit money banks in Nigeria and failure on this from leads to failure of banks. As such they used three variables that measure credit risk namely: ratio of non-performing loans to total credit (RNPC) - (that is, default ratio arrived at by dividing non-performing loans and advances by total loans and advances; ratio of nonperforming loans and advances by total loans and advances; ratio of non-performing loans to total deposits (RNPD); and ratio of non-performing loans shareholder’s fund (RNPS). (Musyoki & Kadubo, 2012).

Model Specification

As specified in Ogbolu and Eze (2016), but a slightly modified version is presented below. Given that the study is aimed at establishing relationships between variable, we employed the Panel regression and correlation analysis technique, expressed functionally as:

$$ROE = f(CTA, NPLR, LLPR, LTDR, TDTA) \dots \dots \dots 1$$

$$ROTA = f(CTA, NPLR, LLPR, LTDR, TDTA) \dots \dots \dots 2$$

We can express this model econometrically as:

$$ROTA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CTA_{It} + \beta_2 NPLR_{It} + \beta_3 LLPR_{It} + \beta_4 LTDR_{It} + \beta_5 TDTA_{It} + u_1 \dots \dots 3$$

$$ROE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CTA_{It} + \beta_2 NPLR_{It} + \beta_3 LLPR_{It} + \beta_4 LTDR_{It} + \beta_5 TDTA_{It} + u_1 \dots \dots 4$$

Where:

ROTA = Return on Total Asset

ROE = Return on Equity

CTA = Capital to Asset Ratio

NPLR = Non Performing Loan Ratio

LLPR = Loan Loss Provision Ratio

LTDR = Loan to Deposit Ratio

TDTA = Total Debt to Total Asset Ratio

β_0 = intercepts

$\beta_1 \dots \beta_5$ = coefficients to be estimated

$u_1 \dots u_2$ are the error terms respectively.

Apriori expectation, $\beta_{1-5} > 0$

Population and Sample Size of the Study

The population and sample of this study comprise of the 12 deposit money banks’ in Nigeria. The period covered is 2006-2018.

Data for the study were collected over the period 2006 to 2018 and were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation Annual Reports.

4. Data Presentation and Analysis

Data is presented in the appendix session of the paper.

Table 4.1: The Descriptive Statistics

	ROA	CTA	LLPR	LTDR	NPLR	TDTA
Mean	1.647692	18.13308	-2.559231	70.68692	4.073077	85.43154
Median	1.850000	19.25000	-1.210000	76.35000	2.180000	86.78000
Maximum	2.570000	48.21000	0.000000	88.91000	21.02000	91.36000
Minimum	0.420000	1.650000	-9.440000	48.80000	0.000000	75.74000
Std. Dev.	0.645994	12.03301	2.991566	15.41571	5.390889	4.209951
Skewness	-0.451941	0.734298	-1.602502	-0.229870	2.361557	-0.991540
Kurtosis	2.255876	3.731551	3.955946	1.394058	7.720913	3.315889
Jarque-Bera	8.909710	17.49762	72.70820	18.13768	289.8663	26.21054
Probability	0.011622	0.000159	0.000000	0.000115	0.000000	0.000002
Sum	257.0400	2828.760	-399.2400	11027.16	635.4000	13327.32
Sum Sq. Dev.	64.68277	22442.97	1387.168	36834.84	4504.561	2747.172
Observations	156	156	156	156	156	156

Source: Researcher’s Computation 2022

The summary statistics above reveals the mean, median, maximum and minimum values, standard deviation, etc of the variables in the model. As such, the result shows not too wide a disparity between means of the explained and the explanatory variables in the model, except or those of LTDR and TDTA. The standard deviation of the variables of interest further reveals evidences of not wide a differences between the means of the dependent as against the respective independent variables under study. The test of normality is also being validated by the kurtosis value of variables in the model of distribution, which is further substantiated by the jarque-bera probability values in the model. More so, while variables like ROA, LLPR, LTDR and TDTA, are skewed to the left (long tail to the left) of the distribution, others of CTA, NPLR, are skewed to the right (long tail to the right hand side of the distribution).

Furthermore, the table also reveals meaningful difference between minimum and maximum values of variables considered in the model. The minimum and maximum values being -9.44 & 91.4. respectively and the jarquebera probability values of variables have a 5% and 1% significance level.

Table 4.2: Correlation Results

	ROA	CTA	LLPR	LTDR	NPLR	TDTA
ROA	1.000000					
CTA	0.293272	1.000000				
LLPR	0.446449	-0.646172	1.000000			
LTDR	0.066586	-0.364819	0.487749	1.000000		
NPLR	-0.535552	-0.277012	-0.125749	0.422336	1.000000	
TDTA	0.496261	0.534327	-0.027533	-0.392609	-0.830666	1.000000

Source: Researcher’s Computation 2022

Discussion of Findings

This shows relationship and movement of variables in the same or different directions in the model. It shows the direction and strength of relationship amongst variables of interest in the model. From the result above, it is clear that variable like NPLR, has rather weak and negative relationship with the dependent variable (ROA), while others of CTA, LLPR, LTDR & TDTA, are seen to have a rather positive and not too strong relationship with the dependent variable of ROA: especially those of LTDR that has a positive but weak relationship with ROA in the model. Similarly, the relationship (correlation) of ROA with itself, as well as those of the respective explanatory variables in the model of distribution is seen to be 1. Furthermore, the implication of the results shows that, with the negative relationship, an increase in non-performing loan ratio (as a credit risk variable in the model), will yield a corresponding decrease in performance by -0.535 unit in the Nigerian deposit money banks within the period of study.

Table 4.5a: Panel Regression Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	10.06168	1.043727	9.640138	0.0000
CTA	0.048010	0.004362	11.00659	0.0000
LLPR	0.197142	0.017863	11.03638	0.0000
LTDR	-0.012775	0.002738	-4.665047	0.0000
NPLR	-0.029673	0.009113	-3.256109	0.0014
TDTA	-0.099833	0.012124	-8.234222	0.0000
R-squared	0.864684			
Adjusted R-squared	0.858284			
S.E. of regression	0.243186			
Sum squared resid	8.752607			
Log likelihood	3.324936			
F-statistic	135.1053	Durbin-Watson		
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000	stat	2.084861	

Source: Researchers’ Computation (2022) using Eviews 7.0

Table 4.5b: Panel Regression Results (ROE as dependent variable)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	10.06168	1.043727	9.640138	0.0000
CTA	0.048010	0.004362	11.00659	0.0000
LLPR	0.197142	0.017863	11.03638	0.0000
LTDR	-0.012775	0.002738	-4.665047	0.0000
NPLR	-0.029673	0.009113	-3.256109	0.0014
TDTA	-0.099833	0.012124	-8.234222	0.0000
R-squared	0.864684			
Adjusted R-squared	0.858284			
S.E. of regression	0.243186			
Sum squared resid	8.752607			
Log likelihood	3.324936			
F-statistic	135.1053	Durbin-Watson		
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000	stat	2.084861	

Source: Researchers’ Computation (2022) using Eviews 7.0

Discussion of Findings

As it may be seen from table 4.5a and 4.5b, respectively above, it represent the panel regression results that emanated from the equations of the model of study of thee paper. Tables 4.5a, represent the panel regression result, using ROA as the dependent variable, while tables 4.5b, stands for the panel regression results, having ROE, as the dependent variable. From the results, in comparison, it is discovered that the panel regression results having ROE, as the dependent variable, had two variables which were not significantly imparting on the dependent variable withn the period of study. While from the panel regression with ROA, as the dependent variable, it is discovered that all the variables of the model significantly impacted on the dependent variable, which therefore made it a better model of estimation of the paper. Also the Durbin Watson statistics shows better result in tables 4.5a than in tables 4.5b, which may be a case of autocorrelation. And while the Durbin Watson statistics in 4.5a reads 2.0, the one in 4.5b only red 2.32.

As such, in table 4.5a, it is observed that all the independent as well as their relationship with the dependent variable conform to the apriori expectation of the study. In other words, the positive relationship of the respective independent variable agrees with the position in theory. The Durbin Watson statistics reports a rather absence result in the model. The overall test process and eliminates suspicion of spurious regression result in the model. The overall test of significance shows that variables in the model passed the test at 1% significance level, at the 99% confidence level. This is revealed by the F-statistic of 0.000000. And more so, from the result in table 4.5a, two variables of the independent variables are negatively signed, which contravene the theoretical expectation (the airport expectation) of having a positive relationship with the dependent variable. The three (3) independent variables are the NPLR, TDTA & LTDR variable in the model.

Furthermore, the coefficient of determination and the adjusted coefficient of determination for the degrees of freedom, denoted by the R2, respectively, reveals that about 86 & 85% systematic variation in the dependent variable of ROA, can be explained by the combination of the independent variables, while about 14 & 15% unexplained variation of the dependent variable is attributed to the stochastic error term in the model. Also,

considering the respective coefficients of the explanatory variables shows that a unit change in CTA, will yield about 0.0480 units change in ROA over the period. This implies that a unit change in CTA will result in an increase in ROA by 0.048units. The same goes for LLPR variable, a unit change in the variable will bring about 0.197 unit increase in the dependent variable of ROA, over the period off study. Moreover, the Hausman test statistics is showed below.

Table 4.5c: Hausman's test statistics

Variable	Fixed	Random
CTA	0.048010	0.048010
LLPR	0.197142	0.197142
LTDR	-0.012775	-0.012775
NPLR	-0.029673	-0.029673
TDTA	-0.099833	-0.099833

The random effect – Hausman test statistics shows the choice of the fixed effect over the random effect considering the probability value of 1.0000,while the cross section random effect variance is set to zero,

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The paper is an analysis of credit risk and performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria and summarily, finding suggest that credit risk management indicators under study significantly affect the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria during the period off study. But the measure of relationship differs according to the different performance indicators. Therefore, the result of our econometric tests leads us to conclude that there is a significant relationship between the various credit risk management indicators employed in this study and the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Also the result of the two models suggests in strong terms that ROA is a better measure of performance than ROE. The following are however recommended to better improve performance and profitability of the Nigerian deposit money banks.

1. The regulators (CBN for policy making purpose) should regularly assess the lending attitudes of deposit money banks and encourage effective cash management policies to avoid insolvency in the financial systems.
2. Banks should not always be in a rush in approving loans for prospective borrowers but should first determine the credit worthiness of the customer so as to aid quick pay back off the loan. This will not only reduce the massive loan losses often witness by them, it will also reduce their huge provision for loss loans and thereby improving their performance over time.
3. Management of deposit money banks need to improve strategies of setting up a credit policy that will not negatively affect the operations of their banks to ensure effective utilization of deposits and maximization of profit and boost liquidity level in the system.

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APPENDIX

DATE	ROA	ROE	LTDR	LLPR	NPLR	TDTA	CTA	Companies
2006	0.42	2.55	48.8	-9.01	4.08	83.45	26.5	Access Bank
2007	1.85	21.43	52.5	-9.44	0.71	91.36	48.21	Access Bank
2008	1.52	9.22	69.49	-0.59	0.21	83.56	3.33	Access Bank
2009	0.63	2.61	87.51	-4.01	21.02	75.74	9.31	Access Bank
2010	1.38	6.31	88.26	-1.05	8.77	78.21	3.16	Access Bank
2011	0.94	7.8	52.3	-1.57	1.8	88.21	1.65	Access Bank
2012	2.57	18.61	50.28	-1.79	2.17	86.19	23.22	Access Bank
2013	2.04	15.34	59.05	-0.78	2.87	86.78	23.94	Access Bank
2014	2.05	15.52	76.35	-1.05	2.27	86.82	19.25	Access Bank
2015	2.54	17.91	81.14	-1.04	1.79	85.81	18.46	Access Bank
2016	2.05	15.72	86.61	-1.21	2.18	86.95	20.49	Access Bank
2017	1.51	12.03	88.91	-1.73	5.08	87.43	23.25	Access Bank
2018	1.92	19.36	77.73	0	0	90.1	14.96	Access Bank
2006	2.66	12.54	49.06	-0.78	20.5	78.66	10.1	Fidelity Bank
2007	2.16	15.66	39.86	-4.18	9.03	86.21	9.04	Fidelity Bank
2008	2.49	9.73	60.54	-0.77	12.01	74.38	5.77	Fidelity Bank
2009	0.28	1.11	60.41	-1.8	22.37	74.44	4.92	Fidelity Bank
2010	1.27	4.49	48.83	-2.24	43.53	71.72	5.3	Fidelity Bank
2011	0.35	1.88	49.53	-1.6	8.16	80.2	11.15	Fidelity Bank
2012	1.99	11.27	48.2	-1.33	3.29	82.34	12.83	Fidelity Bank
2013	0.71	4.72	52.85	-1.91	3.24	84.88	19.22	Fidelity Bank
2014	1.16	7.97	66.06	-0.79	3.29	85.42	21.75	Fidelity Bank
2015	1.13	7.58	75.13	-1	3.53	85.1	15.05	Fidelity Bank
2016	0.75	5.25	90.6	-1.21	4.63	85.72	15.95	Fidelity Bank
2017	1.37	9.27	99.16	-1.47	2.09	85.26	19.55	Fidelity Bank
2018	1.33	11.79	86.77	0	0	88.7	22.38	Fidelity Bank
2006	2.82	27.04	39.5	-2.25	2.76	100	8.27	First Bank Holding
2007	2.26	24.68	36.35	-0.92	3.08	90.82	6.79	First Bank Holding
2008	2.39	10.27	65.61	-1.31	1.59	76.72	5.83	First Bank Holding
2009	0.23	1.57	80.09	-1.8	8.72	85.68	3.24	First Bank Holding
2010	1.45	9.81	78.84	-1.89	8.1	85.22	3.28	First Bank Holding
2011	0.65	5.06	64.19	-3.03	2.69	87.11	6.97	First Bank Holding
2012	2.37	17.24	64.21	-0.81	1.41	86.23	9.43	First Bank Holding
2013	1.82	14.97	60.4	-1.15	1.83	87.81	15.35	First Bank Holding
2014	1.91	15.84	71.42	-1.19	2.41	87.96	16.08	First Bank Holding
2015	0.36	2.62	61.17	-6.57	18.61	86.11	17.18	First Bank Holding
2016	0.36	2.94	67.13	-10.85	27.39	87.7	14.57	First Bank Holding
2017	0.91	7.05	63.67	-7.52	24.53	87.05	12.26	First Bank Holding
2018	1.07	11.26	48.29	0	0	90.47	11.73	First Bank Holding
2006	2.66	10.74	27.13	-0.12	43.28	75.26	13.44	First City Monumental Bank
2007	2.26	19.13	44.53	-1.81	3.28	88.17	9.65	First City Monumental Bank
2008	3.23	11.31	70.16	-1.69	2.83	71.41	5.76	First City Monumental Bank
2009	0.12	0.44	71.3	-8.54	12.51	72.05	1.94	First City Monumental Bank

2010	1.47	5.89	79.6	-9.63	4.43	74.98	2.49	First City Monumental Bank
2011	-1.54	-7.87	50.04	-8.56	4.47	80.47	8.05	First City Monumental Bank
2012	1.66	11.45	50.03	-3.55	1.43	85.47	13.59	First City Monumental Bank
2013	1.59	11.13	62.99	-1.77	1.21	85.75	19.81	First City Monumental Bank
2014	1.89	13.8	84.22	-1.72	1.32	86.29	10.8	First City Monumental Bank
2015	0.41	2.93	84.68	-2.54	2.53	86	15.6	First City Monumental Bank
2016	1.22	8.02	100	-5.38	1.89	84.75	9.22	First City Monumental Bank
2017	0.79	4.98	94.19	-3.49	3.34	84.07	8.76	First City Monumental Bank
2018	1.05	8.16	77.04	0	0	87.18	12.94	First City Monumental Bank
2006	2.69	20.38	39.02	-2.12	3.52	86.78	24.01	Guaranty Trust Bank
2007	2.71	26.4	39.3	-0.64	2.08	89.73	26.18	Guaranty Trust Bank
2008	3.11	16.43	88.15	-1.14	1.87	81.09	29.33	Guaranty Trust Bank
2009	2.68	14.88	82.49	-5.91	12.57	81.97	3.37	Guaranty Trust Bank
2010	3.33	18.19	77.98	-1.75	7.24	81.7	2.5	Guaranty Trust Bank
2011	3.09	20.89	68.89	-2.76	3.25	85.19	22.85	Guaranty Trust Bank
2012	5	30.9	67.85	-0.09	3.44	83.83	15.96	Guaranty Trust Bank
2013	4.28	27.51	70.22	-0.29	3.37	84.44	14.62	Guaranty Trust Bank
2014	4.19	26.37	78.83	-0.56	3.06	84.11	10.48	Guaranty Trust Bank
2015	3.94	24.04	85.19	-0.9	3.04	83.62	10.09	Guaranty Trust Bank
2016	4.24	26.2	80.02	-4.11	3.8	83.8	14.63	Guaranty Trust Bank
2017	5.09	27.78	70.25	-0.84	8.02	81.69	19.16	Guaranty Trust Bank
2018	5.62	32.08	55.37	0	0	82.49	20.59	Guaranty Trust Bank
2006	3.52	12.19	86.73	-0.41	25.2	70.99	5.53	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2007	3.63	13.99	74.57	-2.03	23.83	68.92	5.34	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2008	4.44	14.87	103.29	-5.1	15.79	70.11	4.29	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2009	3.13	10.11	65.31	-4.4	16.02	69.02	2.99	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2010	2.46	11.29	87.93	-0.38	7.26	77.86	2.61	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2011	1.2	8.32	97.72	-1.11	5.47	84.71	5.43	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2012	1.5	12.19	82	-2.15	4.47	87.35	11.37	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2013	3.12	22.03	89.07	-0.63	3.18	85.33	12.4	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2014	3.39	26.67	77.73	-0.74	0	87.9	12.33	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2015	2.01	14.65	60.02	-17.56	7.65	86.24	22.56	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2016	2.71	20.26	57.42	-5.61	5.29	86.64	28.6	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2017	3.49	26.12	49.37	-6.87	8.52	86.64	28.95	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2018	4.47	31.06	45.59	0	0	85.59	27.4	Stanbic Ibtc Holding
2006	0.96	4.12	55.91	-0.25	30.72	76.57	16.09	Sterling Bank
2007	1.51	6.94	47.48	-7.71	30.57	100	38.16	Sterling Bank
2008	3.01	20.94	37.8	-4.68	9.77	85.6	46.22	Sterling Bank
2009	-4.92	-40.74	59.99	-16.08	23.61	87.93	4.67	Sterling Bank
2010	2.16	19.17	54.98	-1.58	11.54	88.72	2.86	Sterling Bank
2011	1.49	16.87	39.55	-3.51	5.08	91.13	19.55	Sterling Bank
2012	1.3	14.91	49.14	0.13	3.06	91.26	18.27	Sterling Bank
2013	1.28	13.04	71.14	-2	1.32	90.15	14.03	Sterling Bank
2014	1.09	10.63	70.8	-1.57	2.1	89.73	17.48	Sterling Bank
2015	1.29	10.77	57.32	-2.41	4.51	88.05	14.5	Sterling Bank
2016	0.62	6.03	80.08	-2.5	1.73	89.73	12.93	Sterling Bank

2017	0.79	8.28	87.33	-2.05	3.75	90.4	11.44	Sterling Bank
2018	0.84	9.43	81.65	0	0	91.13	10.67	Sterling Bank
2008	2.68	21.44	37.95	-2.24	67.08	87.52	4.68	Union Bank Of Nig
2009	-20.23	122.8	49.06	-42.22	75.64	116.48	6.25	Union Bank Of Nig
2010	9.54	-91.95	31.33	-18.36	58.38	110.37	2.19	Union Bank Of Nig
2011	-7.83	-42	33.17	-8.08	10.66	81.1	22.66	Union Bank Of Nig
2012	0.71	3.79	31.57	-0.94	11.19	81.18	19.39	Union Bank Of Nig
2013	0.61	3.05	47.55	-5.26	6.36	80.12	10.06	Union Bank Of Nig
2014	2.63	11.95	59.28	-1.54	5.41	77.98	12.09	Union Bank Of Nig
2015	1.33	5.69	64.26	-2.71	7.07	76.7	7.86	Union Bank Of Nig
2016	1.23	5.67	77.03	-3.27	7.3	78.31	10.87	Union Bank Of Nig
2017	1	4.23	64.45	0	0	76.25	15.29	Union Bank Of Nig
2018	1.24	8.02	55.21	0	0	84.59	15.96	Union Bank Of Nig
2006	1.31	23.8	14.41	-5.07	13.74	94.48	9.03	United Bank For Africa
2007	2.1	12.78	35.37	-1.16	4.58	100	12.7	United Bank For Africa
2008	2.76	21.1	32.36	-0.61	3.75	86.91	8.12	United Bank For Africa
2009	0.17	1.27	51.12	-6.26	8.43	86.28	5.01	United Bank For Africa
2010	0.04	0.33	49.62	-2.9	4.21	87.52	4.73	United Bank For Africa
2011	-0.49	-5.74	41.89	-2.93	2.8	91.47	24.54	United Bank For Africa
2012	2.47	26.75	38.31	-0.69	2.04	90.75	34.32	United Bank For Africa
2013	1.76	19.83	43.38	-1.39	1.25	91.1	27.13	United Bank For Africa
2014	1.73	18.05	49.4	-0.3	1.65	90.39	29.41	United Bank For Africa
2015	2.17	17.93	49.8	-0.49	0.65	87.92	23.81	United Bank For Africa
2016	2.06	16.13	1380	-1.84	1.45	87.21	21.71	United Bank For Africa
2017	1.93	14.84	60.4	-1.99	1.73	86.99	22.07	United Bank For Africa
2018	1.61	15.64	51.22	0	0	89.68	25.06	United Bank For Africa
2007	0.35	2.25	25.1	-12.81	104.74	84.24	20.72	Unity Bank
2008	-3.72	-66.88	16.2	-56.9	24.81	94.43	3.55	Unity Bank
2009	-6.43	-233.1	40.85	-16.21	14.7	97.24	3.1	Unity Bank
2010	4.78	28.44	51.41	-5.96	17.22	83.19	6.66	Unity Bank
2011	1.03	6.15	44.17	-2.36	4.04	83.2	10.62	Unity Bank
2012	1.8	12.01	70	-0.72	3.04	85.05	11.98	Unity Bank
2013	-5.59	-80.04	64.37	-11.06	29.49	93.01	2.41	Unity Bank
2014	2.59	14.02	79.18	-7.92	21.33	81.55	1.65	Unity Bank
2015	1.06	5.68	106.35	-11.02	24.33	81.37	6.22	Unity Bank
2016	0.44	2.63	104.93	-12.97	33.58	83.13	10.38	Unity Bank
2017	-9.53	6.16	3.55	0	0	254.75	3.63	Unity Bank
2018	0.54	-0.52	18.05	0	0	203.27	3.76	Unity Bank
2006	-5.5	-32.14	62.73	-12.1	78.74	82.9	24.12	Wema Bank
2007	1.83	10.14	54.83	-11.77	30.76	82	25.14	Wema Bank
2008	1.83	10.14	54.83	0	30.76	82	25.14	Wema Bank
2009	-3.83	16.43	31.9	-14.31	235.36	123.29	3.23	Wema Bank
2010	8.68	110.69	35.4	50.28	86.85	92.16	3.26	Wema Bank
2011	-1.97	-67.47	45.62	-3.41	15.93	97.08	11.14	Wema Bank
2012	-2.06	-394.3	42.31	-6.72	13.56	99.48	8.03	Wema Bank
2013	0.55	3.86	45.3	1.35	4.13	85.7	10.82	Wema Bank

2014	0.62	5.42	57.65	-0.06	1.03	88.56	13.63	Wema Bank
2015	0.59	5.05	65.13	0.04	1.41	88.39	14.26	Wema Bank
2016	0.6	5.28	80.13	-0.18	2.33	88.57	6.51	Wema Bank
2017	0.58	4.55	84.82	0	0	87.22	0.58	Wema Bank
2018	0.68	6.54	68.31	0	0	89.59	8.62	Wema Bank
2006	1.88	11.55	50.91	-0.65	1.15	83.75	58.96	Zenith Bank
2007	1.93	16.13	45.41	-0.64	1.4	88.03	59.1	Zenith Bank
2008	2.91	15	37.91	-1.41	2.13	80.6	13.41	Zenith Bank
2009	1.24	6.1	59.49	-5.71	6.93	79.65	7.64	Zenith Bank
2010	2.44	10.36	54.12	-0.61	6.21	76.41	9.25	Zenith Bank
2011	2.52	12.44	53.99	-1.85	2.47	79.74	11.55	Zenith Bank
2012	4.7	21.9	51.31	-0.92	1.46	78.53	15.53	Zenith Bank
2013	3.62	18.87	54.96	-0.88	1.11	80.82	22.27	Zenith Bank
2014	2.65	18	68.16	-11.18	0.58	85.28	20.04	Zenith Bank
2015	2.64	17.78	77.77	-0.79	2.26	85.17	19.01	Zenith Bank
2016	2.74	18.4	76.73	-1.41	3.12	85.14	14.12	Zenith Bank
2017	3.18	21.66	61.09	-4.68	4.04	85.32	17.12	Zenith Bank
2018	0.32	23.71	49.4	0	0	8.63	1.6	Zenith Bank